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FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS STUDY OF PNB AND HDFC BANK

Bhanwar Singh

Research Scholar

IMSAR, Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak-124001 (India)

Pawan

Research Scholar

IMSAR, Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak-124001 (India)

ABSTRACT

Bank is back bone of an economy's financial system. Financial inclusion is the main need of an economy. Banks and others financial institutions play paramount role in financial inclusion of an economy of country. Today's globalised economies, banks are safe source of finance to individual and corporations. The knowledge of financial performance helps, to decision makers, in predicting, comparing, and evaluating the earning ability of company. Company provides financial information through annual reports and financial bulletin. A company's financial performance can be determined by evaluating and analyzing the data provided in its annual reports and financial bulletin. This research study is descriptive and analytical in nature. The data use for this study is entirely secondary in nature. In this study, financial performance of PNB and HDFC Bank is evaluates and compare. The study shows PNB face the problems to generate the income and NPAs of PNB is increasing. The study shows that the financial performance of HDFC Bank is better than PNB.

KEYWORDS: *Capital Adequacy Ratio, Credit Deposit Ratio, Net Profit, NPAs, Return on Average Assets.*

INTRODUCTION

Bank is back bone of an economy's financial system. Banks accepts deposits from public and provides credit facility to productive firms and business entity in form of loans. The Indian banking system is featured by a large network of bank branches and its ATMs, serving many types of financial needs of community. A strong banking system helps in rapid growth of economy through credit facility and mobilizes of saving to fund seeking entity. In recent years, Government of India and Reserve Bank of India, has given more focus on financial inclusion through strong financial institution like Banks. Today, in India every corner of country has accessible to banking facilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Svetlana Tatuskar (2010), in his research paper took the sample of 5 commercial banks (SBI, ICICI, AXIS, HDFC, BOI) in India to analysis the financial performance of banks through Camels methodology for 2006-2010. The paper also compared the performance of these Banks with the previous year 2008-09 and ranks each bank on the basis of the findings got by the CAMEL methodology evaluations. The study showed that the performance of the banks for the year ended 2010 had been much better as against their performance during the previous year ended 2009. With the effect of the crisis subsidizing in the global banking sector, the Indian banking sector had shown extraordinary financial performance even amidst the financial crisis.

M. Dhanabhakym, M. Kavitha (2012) in their study on “Financial Performance of Selected Public Sector Banks in India” explained that the banks have to re-orient their strategies in the light of their own strengths and the kind of market in which they are likely to operate on. In the perspective of this domestic and international development, the banking sector has to chart out a perfect path for the development in its own.

Faisal Abbas, Muhammad Tahir, Mutee-ur-Rahman (2012) in their article on “ A comparison of Financial Performance in Banking Sector: Some Evidence from Pakistani Commercial Banks” concluded that ranking of top five Pakistani commercial Banks based on their total average assets, total operating fixed assets, total average equity and return on respective variable.

Cheenu Goel and C B Rekhi (2013) had analyzed the performance of three major public sector banks (SBI, PNB, BOB) and three private sector banks (ICICI, HDFC, AXIS) year 2009 to 2012. To analysis the data ratios and coefficient correlation techniques were employed. The foregoing analysis for SBI had revealed that the overall profitability is not that high because they there NIM is less and need to increase NIM. For PNB return on equity was very high as compared to other banks and they have good association with deposits. In case of BOB bank doesn't have good association with deposits so there CDR is also very less and NIM is also need to gear up. For ICICI bank it has good association with CAR and deposits in banks are very high and NIM is less which needs to be increased which will impact the profitability. For HDFC it has very high CDR which is great sign for increase in profitability and in this case NIM and deposits are high which has drastically impacted the

NP. For AXIS ROA is quite high as compared to other banks and is negative associated with CAR. Profitability is positive associated with NIM and CDR.

A Chandani, M. Mehta, B Neeraja (2014) in his research paper on “Women CEOs and Financial Performance of Banks: An empirical research of Indian Private Sector Banks” tried to measure and analyze the influence of two successful women (Chanda Kochhar and Shikha Sharma) to their performance. They took the sample of ICICI Bank and Axis Bank. They used the secondary data of both banks in his study, they used the CAMEL rating system for performance analysis. The t-test was also used to measure the impact of female leadership on the net profit of the banks, which proved that there was a significant difference between the two leaders i.e. the net profit of the banks improved when the women assumed the leadership role in the banks.

Jeevan Jayant Nagarkar (2015) his study on "Analysis of Financial Performance of Banks in India" wanted to know the effect of recession 2008 in banking sector. In his study, he took 15 banks sample for study purpose and classified in three categories Public, Private and Foreign banks 5 banks in each category. In his paper, he attempt to find out how banks have performed on financial parameters during last year 5 years compared to high growth year. He divided financial performance of banks is compared in two period of time before recession 2008 and after. He compared financial performance of banks High growth years of 2004-08 with Low growth period years of 2009-2013. In his study, he found banks are better if they depend on deposit rather than borrowed money for disbursing advances. He found that large national level banks are able to withstand business cycles better than region banks.

K. V. Bhanumurthy (2015) People have misconception or the myth that the main banking business is accepting deposits and lending loans. The profitability of banks is reducing because of high level of non-performing assets. However the reality is that the banks are aggressively involving in off balance sheet business, particularly the foreign banks that can at any time threaten and destroy the stability of banks.

Dharmendra S. Mistry, Vijay Savani (2015) has tried to analyze the financial performance of privet sector banks on the basis of Return on Assets and Interest Income Size. They used Correlations and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for testing hypothesis. The study found that Return on Assets and Interest Income size have negative correlation with operational

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efficiency, whereas positive correlation with Assets Utilization and Assets size. It is also revealed from the study that there exists an impact of operational efficiency, assets management and bank size on financial performance of the Indian Private Sector Banks.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To study and compare the financial performance of PNB and HDFC Bank through ratios analysis.

The main hypothesis of the present study is:

H_0 There is no significant difference between financial performance of PNB and HDFC bank.

The sub hypotheses of the study are:

$H_{0.1}$ There is no significant difference between Return on Average Assets ratio of PNB and HDFC bank.

$H_{0.2}$ There is no significant difference between Capital Adequacy Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank.

$H_{0.3}$ There is no significant difference between Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank.

$H_{0.4}$ There is no significant difference between Cost to Income Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank.

$H_{0.5}$ There is no significant difference between Credit Deposit Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank.

$H_{0.6}$ There is no significant difference between Profit per Employee of PNB and HDFC bank.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the present, an effort has been made to assess, evaluate and compare the financial performance of PNB and HDFC Bank which one belong to the public sector and private sector respectively. The present study based on purely secondary data that has been collected from annual reports of both banks, magazines, articles published in journals, other published

documents and websites have been chosen when found relevant. The study covers the period of 5 years i.e. year 2010-11 to year 2014-15. Generally, most of the past studies made on financial performance of commercial banks based on different financial variables such like Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital (ROC). Ratio analysis is applied to analysis and compares the trends in banking business and financial performance. To check the trends in banking business profitability Annual Growth Rate (AGR) and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is used. To test the hypothesis Mann-Whitney U-test has employed also.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Ratios

Return on Average Assets Ratio

Return on Average Ratio is an indicator used to assess the profitability of a bank's assets and it is calculated by taking net income and divided by average total assets. The ratio helps to measure how efficiently a bank is utilizing its assets. The higher the ROAA of a bank indicate more the profitability of bank.

Capital Adequacy Ratio

Capital adequacy ratio is an instrument to measure the financial health of banks. This ratio is used to protect the interest of depositors and promote the stability and financial efficiency system. Reserve Bank of India (RBI) presently directed to commercial banks to maintain a minimum capital of 9% of risk-weighted assets.

Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio

NPA is a disorder resulting in non-performance of a portion of loan portfolio leading to no recovery or less recovery / income to the lender. NPAs are an inevitable burden on the banking sector. The success of a bank depends upon the methods of managing NPAs and keeping them within tolerance level (Misra & Yadav, 2015)

Cost to Income Ratio

Cost to income ratio represents the ability of management to income generate at low level of cost. CI ratio measure the income generated per rupee cost. If a bank produced more income

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per rupee cost compare to other bank then performance banks would be better. Low level of cost to income ratio indicates better performance of bank and better management of bank.

Credit Deposit Ratio

Credit-Deposit Ratio is the proportion of loan-assets created by a bank from the deposits received. Credits are the loans and advances granted by the bank. In other words it is the amount lent by the bank to a person or an organization which is recovered later on. Interest is charged from the borrower. Deposit is the amount accepted by bank from the savers and interest is paid to them. (B.Singh & Tandon, 2012) .

$$\text{Credit Deposit Ratio} = \text{Credit} / \text{Deposit}$$

Profit per Employee

Profit per Employee represents the profit per employee. It shows the operating performance of banks. Higher the ratio indicates better operating performance of bank. Profit per Employee ratio= Revenue/ Number of employee

Table 1: Total Number of Branches of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC Bank	
	No. of Branches	AGR (%)	No. of Branches	AGR (%)
2009-10	5002	-	1725	-
2010-11	5189	3.74	1986	15.13
2011-12	5670	9.27	2544	28.10
2012-13	5874	3.60	3062	20.36
2013-14	6201	5.57	3403	11.14
2014-15	6560	5.89	4014	17.95

Source: Annual reports of PNB and HDFC Bank for FY 2010-11 to 2014-15.

Table 1 presents the trends in total number of branches of PNB and HDFC Bank. It shows that total number of branches of both banks is increasing year on year.

Figure 1: Trends in AGR of Total Number of Branches

Figure 1 shows the trends in AGR of Total Number of Branches of PNB and HDFC Banks. It shows that AGR of PNB is less than HDFC Bank whole years. Figure reveals that rate of increase in total number of branches in case of HDFC Bank is more than PNB. It indicates that performance of PNB in terms of growth in total number of branches is diminishing as compared to HDFC Banks.

Table 2: Total Number of ATMs of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	No. of ATMs	AGR (%)	No. of ATMs	AGR (%)
2009-10	3544	-	4232	-
2010-11	5050	42.49	5471	29.28
2011-12	6009	18.99	8913	62.91
2012-13	6313	5.06	10743	20.53
2013-14	6940	9.93	11256	4.78
2014-15	8348	20.29	11766	4.53

Source: Annual reports of PNB and HDFC Bank for FY 2010-11 to 2014-15.

Table 2 shows trends in AGR of Total Number of ATMs of PNB and HDFC Bank. Table reveals that total number of ATMs of both banks is increasing by year on year. In case of Total number of ATMs HDFC Banks maintain huge gap from PNB.

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Figure 2: Trends in AGR of Total Number of ATMs

Figure 2 shows trends in AGR of total number of ATMs of PNB and HDFC Bank. Figure shows that AGR of total number of ATMs of PNB is diminishing for the year 2010-11 to 2012-13. After FY 2012-13 AGR of total number of ATMs of PNB is increasing upto FY 2014-15. On other hand, figure reveals that FY 2010-11 to FY 2011-12 AGR of total number of ATMs of HDFC Bank is increasing also high to PNB. But after FY 2011-12 AGR of total number of ATMs of HDFC Bank is decreasing upto FY 2014-15. It indicates that last three years performance of PNB in term of AGR in total of ATMs is noticeable.

Table 3: Net Profit PNB and HDFC Bank

(FY 2010-11 to 2014-15) (Amount in Crore Rs.)

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	Amount	AGR (%)	Amount	AGR (%)
2009-10	3905	-	2949	-
2010-11	4433	13.52	3926	33.13
2011-12	4884	10.17	5167	31.61
2012-13	4748	-2.78	6726	30.17
2013-14	3343	-29.59	8478	26.05
2014-15	3062	-8.41	10216	20.5
CAGR		-17.09		141.46

Source: Annual reports of PNB and HDFC Bank for FY 2010-11 to 2014-15.

Table 3 shows the trends in net profit of PNB and HDFC Bank. Table reveals information about the CAGR of both banks. It presents that CAGR for net profit of HDFC Bank is more than PNB. Gap between CAGR for net profit of PNB is too far from HDFC Bank.

Figure 3 Trends in AGR of NET Profit of Banks

Figure 3 shows the trends in AGR of NET Profit of PNB and HDFC Bank. It shows AGR for net profits of HDFC Bank is positive all years but diminishing year on year and CAGR for net profit of bank (141.46) is more than PNB. On other side AGR for net profits of PNB is diminishing and it negative after FY 2011-12 to upto end and CAGR for net profit of PNB (-17.09) is negative. Table indicates that performance of HDFC Bank in term of net profit is better compare to PNB.

The hypotheses of present of study were tested with the help of Mann-Whitney U-test follows:

H₀ There is no significant difference between Financial Performance of PNB and HDFC Bank.

Table 4: Mann- Whitney U-test for Return on Average Assets Ratio (%) of PNB and HDFC Bank

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FY	PNB		HDFC	
	AAR VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	1.34	5	1.58	6
2011-12	1.19	4	1.77	7
2012-13	1.00	3	1.9	8
2013-14	0.64	2	2.00	9
2014-15	0.53	1	2.02	10
Sum of Rank order		15		40
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	0**			
Z-value	2.61**			

Note: * Significant at p=0.05, ** Significant at p=0.01

Calculating value of U-statistics is 0 which is equal to table value of U-statistics (0) at level of significant 0.01, so it can be said that difference between Return on Average Assets of PNB and HDFC Bank is significant at level of p=0.01. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value (2.61) is more than table value of z-statistics (2.58) at level of p=0.01. So, the null hypothesis $H_{0.1}$ "There is no significant difference between Return on Average Assets ratio of PNB and HDFC bank" is rejected.

Table 5: Mann- Whitney U-test for Capital Adequacy Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	12.42	3	16.22	7
2011-12	12.63	4	16.52	8
2012-13	12.72	5	16.80	10
2013-14	11.52	1	16.07	6
2014-15	12.21	2	16.79	9
Sum of Rank order		15		40
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	0**			
Z-value	2.611**			

Note: * Significant at p=0.05, ** Significant at p=0.01

Calculating value of U-statistics is 0 which is equal to table value of U-statistics (0) at level of significant 0.01, so it can be said that difference between Capital Adequacy Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank is significant at level of p=0.01. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value (2.61) is more than table value of z-statistics (2.58) at level of p=0.01. So, the null

hypothesis $H_{0.2}$ “There is significant difference between Capital Adequacy Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank” is rejected.

Table 6: Mann- Whitney U-test for Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	0.85	6	0.19	2
2011-12	1.52	7	0.18	1
2012-13	2.35	8	0.20	3
2013-14	2.85	9	0.27	5
2014-15	4.06	10	0.25	4
Sum of Rank order		40		15
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	0**			
Z-value	2.611**			

Note: * Significant at $p=0.05$, ** Significant at $p=0.01$

Calculating value of U-statistics is 0 which is equal to table value of U-statistics (0) at level of significant 0.01, so it can be said that difference between Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank is significant at level of $p=0.01$. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value (2.61) is more than table value of z-statistics (2.58) at level of $p=0.01$. So, the null hypothesis $H_{0.3}$ “There is no significant difference between Capital Adequacy Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank” is rejected.

Table 7: Mann- Whitney U-test for Cost to Income Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	41.27	2	48.08	8
2011-12	39.75	1	49.68	10
2012-13	42.81	3	49.58	9
2013-14	45.06	5	45.61	6
2014-15	46.74	7	44.56	4
Sum of Rank order		18		37
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	3			
Z-value	1.98			

Note: * Significant at $p=0.05$, ** Significant at $p=0.01$

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Calculating value of U-statistics is 3 which is more than table value of U-statistics (2) at level of significant 0.05, so it can be said that difference between Cost to Income Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank is not significant at level of $p=0.05$. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value which is lies on acceptance region z-statistics at level of $p=0.05$. So, the null hypothesis $H_{0.4}$ “There is no significant difference between Cost to Income Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank” is accepted.

Table 8: Mann- Whitney U-test for Credit Deposit Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	77.38	3.5	76.7	2
2011-12	77.39	5	79.2	7
2012-13	78.86	6	80.9	8
2013-14	77.38	3.5	81.79	10
2014-15	75.90	1	81.71	9
Sum of Rank order		19		36
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	4			
Z-value	1.78			

Note: * Significant at $p=0.05$, ** Significant at $p=0.01$

Calculating value of U-statistics is 4 which is more than table value of U-statistics (2) at level of significant 0.05, so it can be said that difference between Net NPA to Net Advance Ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank is not significant at level of $p=0.01$. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value (1.78) is less than table value of z-statistics (1.96) at level of $p=0.05$. So, the null hypothesis $H_{0.5}$ “There is no significant difference between Credit Deposit Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank” is accepted.

Table 9: Mann- Whitney U-test for Profit Per Employee of PNB and HDFC Bank (Amount in Crore Rs.)

FY	PNB		HDFC	
	VALUE	RANK	VALUE	RANK
2010-11	8.35	6	7.37	3
2011-12	8.42	7	8.12	5
2012-13	8.06	4	10.00	8.5
2013-14	5.49	2	12.00	10
2014-15	5.00	1	10.00	8.5
Sum of Rank order		20		35
No. of Data	5		5	
U-statistics	5			
Z-value	1.57			

Note: * Significant at $p=0.05$, ** Significant at $p=0.01$

Calculating value of U-statistics is 5 which is more than table value of U-statistics (2) at level of significant 0.05, so it can be said that difference between Profit Per Employee of PNB and HDFC Bank is not significant at level of $p=0.05$. It is further confirmed by calculating z-value (1.57) is less than table value of z-statistics (1.96) at level of $p=0.05$. So, the null hypothesis $H_{0.6}$ "There is no significant difference between Credit Deposit Ratio of PNB and HDFC bank" is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Bank works in dynamic environment which affected by many uncontrollable factors i.e. level of inflation, government and RBI policies, economic conditions and many more factors. It is very difficult to measure the financial performance of banks in presence of these uncontrolled factors. It is concluded from the study, total number of branches of both banks increase by year on year basis but annual growth rate in total number of branches in HDFC Bank is more than PNB which indicates HDFC Bank is invested more fund in construction of branches than to PNB invested in construction of branches.

It is concluded that both bank spend the large fund to construct the ATMs but annual growth rate in total number of ATMs of HDFC Bank is more than annual growth rate in total number of ATMs in PNB.

It shows that HDFC Bank generating more profits to its rival. Annual growth rate in Net profit of HDFC Bank is positive all year which indicate bank performing well but annual growth rate in Net profit of PNB after year 2011-12 is negative which indicate PNB facing huge problems in generating profits.

Return on average assets ratio show that financial performance of HDFC Bank is better than PNB which indicate HDFC Bank invested its assets in more profitable hands. Capital adequacy ratio of HDFC Bank is also higher than PNB which indicate HDFC Bank is more financially healthy to PNB. Net NPAs to Net Assets ratio of HDFC Bank is lower than PNB which shows that HDFC Bank is better to recover its advance but NPAs in case of PNB is increasing year on year which indicates PNB should appraise credit policy to manage the NPAs.

Cost to income ratio of PNB is less than HDFC Banks. Credit deposit ratio of PNB and HDFC Bank both have well. Both banks full utilize its deposits to disburse advances. Profit per employee of HDFC is increasing and PNB is decreasing but during sample period both

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bank profit per employee is not significant. It is concluded from parameters of financial performance of both banks that HDFC Bank performing better than PNB.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, F., Tahir, M., & Rahman, M. U. (2012). A Comparison of Financial Performance in the Banking Sector: Some Evidence from Pakistani Commercial Banks. *Journal of Business Administration and Education* , 1-14.
- Annual reports of HDFC Bank years 2010-2011 to 2014-2015.*
- Annual reports of Punjab National Bank years 2010-2011 to 2014-2015.*
- B.Singh, A., & Tandon, P. (2012). A Study of Financial Performance: A Comparative Analysis of SBI and ICICI Bank. *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research* .
- Bhanumurthy, K. V., & Gupta, L. (2015). "Risk and Return" in Banking Industry in India: Concept and Measurement. *The Indian Journal of Commerce* , 53-63.
- Chandani, A., Mehta, M., & Neeraja, B. (2014). Women CEOs and Financial Performance of Banks: An Emprirical Research of Indian Private Sector. *Management* , 19, 231-246.
- Dhanabhakym, M., & Kavitha, M. (2012). Financial Performance of Selected Pulic Sector Banks in India. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* , 255-269.
- Goel, C., & Bhutani, C. (2013). A Comparative Study on the Performance of Selected Public Sector and Private Sector Banks in India. *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research (JBM&SSR)* , 46-56.
- Levin, R. I., & Rubin, D. S. (1998). *Statistics for Management*. New Delhi: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Misra, P., & Yadav, A. S. (2015). A comparative Study of Financial Performance of SBI and ICICI Bank. *The Indian Journal of Commerce* , 64-70.
- Mistry, D. S., & Savani, V. (2015). A Compaarative Study of the Profitablity Performance in the Banking Sector: Evidence from Indian Private Sector Banks. *XVI Annual Conference Proceedings*, (pp. 346-360).
- Munir, S., Ramzan, M., Iqbal, R. Q., Ahmad, M., & Raza, A. (2012). Financial Performance Assessment of Banks: A Case of Pakistani Public Sector Banks. *International Journal of Business and Social Science* , 276-283.
- Nagarkar, J. J. (2015). Analysis of Financial Performance of Banks in India. *Annual Research Journal of SCMS, Pune* , 26-37.
- Tatuskar, S. (2010). A sudy of Financial Performance of Select Indian Scheduled Commercial Banks Using Camels Methodology for 2006-2010. *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management* , 105-121.